

2D NUMERICAL INVESTIGATION OF PRE-TENSION ON LOW VELOCITY IMPACT DAMAGE OF SANDWICH STRUCTURES

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1 Introduction

Most structural components of an aircraft which are exposed to Foreign Object Damage (FOD) will have a certain degree of pre-load. This pre-load has the potential to cause more damage during impact compared to an unloaded structure, and it is therefore important to understand the effects of pre-load on the impact response.

The body of literature is becoming extensive in the area of impact onto pre-loaded laminates. Research has shown that pre-tension stiffens the elastic impact response [1] by reducing contact duration and deflection, and by increasing the peak force [2]. Studies show that pre-load will cause more damage from an impact if the level of pre-tension is high compared to the tensile strength of the material [3] or if the impactor is sharp, thus inducing more damage [4, 5].

Sandwich structures are becoming increasingly common on aircraft and rotorcraft. For example carbon-epoxy skins with Rohacell foam core are used in stringer-stiffened applications or the blades of a rotorcraft [6]. Though there is much literature on impact of pre-loaded laminates, there has been little work on impact onto pre-loaded sandwich structures. McGowan and Ambur have [7] researched impact onto compressed sandwiches, and Kepler and Bull [8] investigated high velocity impact onto sandwich structures with bending pre-loads. A literature search has not yielded research relating to pre-tensioned sandwich structures.

For numerical analysis, Mikkor and co-workers [9, 10] have modelled pre-tensioned laminates, with damage area over-predicted in all cases, albeit more so for the pre-loaded case. Choi [2] used modified plate deformation theory for his numerical model to

include strain terms to initialise damage, and could thus specify the geometry in the pre-loaded state. The damage, however, was not thoroughly accounted for in this model. Heimbs [11] modelled a honeycomb sandwich under compression and impact using a stacked shell approach and explicitly ramped up the pre-load. Results appear to correlate well with experimental results, but each cell of the core was modelled with shells, which can be time consuming and is impractical for a foam core.

The current study aims to develop a numerical technique to model pre-tension in sandwich structures, then to compare impact onto unloaded sandwich specimens and laminates to impact onto pre-tensioned specimens.

2 Problem Description

Impact of a cylinder onto sandwich panels and laminates has been investigated in this study.

The sandwich panels consist of carbon epoxy VTM264 skin with Rohacell 71WF core and the laminates are equivalent to one of the sandwich specimen's skins. The dimensions of the model are 40 mm wide × 190 mm long. The layup is [(0 90)_{2S} core]_S with each skin having a thickness of 1.6 mm and the core 6 mm. The impactor is cylindrical and impacts across the width of the specimen in order to reduce the model to a two dimensional (2D) problem. The impactor diameter was 12 mm and mass 4 kg.

The test matrix for both the sandwich panels and laminates is shown below in Table 1.

Table 1. Test matrix for both the sandwich and laminate specimens.

Test	Pre-load ($\mu\epsilon$)	Energy (J)
1	0	2
2	0	8
3	0	18
4	2500	2
5	2500	8
6	2500	18
7	5000	2
8	5000	8
9	5000	18

3 Numerical Modelling

3.1 Model Description

A single row of three dimensional (3D) elements was chosen to model the sandwich specimen in LS-DYNA® [12]. The model consisted of 4600 reduced integration, constant stress elements and 10296 nodes. One half of the coupon was modelled due to symmetry. The mass of the impactor was scaled down to account for symmetry. A stiffness based hourglass control was used.

The boundary conditions were clamped at one end and symmetry conditions were modelled at the impact region for both the laminates and sandwich coupons. Symmetry boundary conditions were imposed on nodes in the width direction to restrict the analysis to a 2D problem.

3.2 Material models

A 3D orthotropic material model [12] with a Chang-Chang damage model was used to model the skins with properties shown in Table 2. The symbols ρ , E , ν , G , S , G_{IC} , G_{IIC} and K are the density, elastic moduli, Poisson's ratio, shear moduli, strengths, mode I fracture toughness, mode II fracture toughness and bulk modulus of failed elements respectively. The numbers following E , ν , G and S are the material directions and T and C are tension and compression respectively. The through-thickness strengths and fracture toughness values shown in this table were modelled with cohesive zone modelling as explained later.

For the sandwich specimens, the core was modelled using mat 163 modified crushable foam [12] where the main input is a non-linear stress-strain curve shown in Fig. 1 determined by crush testing.

Table 2. Ply material properties for VTM264.

ρ $g.mm^{-3}$	E_{11T} MPa	E_{22T} MPa	E_{33T} MPa	ν_{21}
0.001538	112500	7467	7467	0.0199
ν_{31}	ν_{32}	G_{12} MPa	G_{13} MPa	G_{23} MPa
0.0199	0.33	4070	4070	2309
S_{11T} MPa	S_{22T} MPa	S_{22C} MPa	S_{33T} MPa	S_{13}, S_{23} MPa
2773	50	100	83	83
G_{IC} $mJ.mm^{-2}$	G_{IIC} $mJ.mm^{-2}$	K MPa		
1.5	2.0	2000		

Fig. 1. Stress-strain curve for Rohacell 71WF

3.3 Contact modelling

The impactor was modelled as a rigid body with a continuous cylindrical curvature and assigned inertial properties.

A tied penalty contact method with a quadratic failure criterion based on maximum normal and shear stresses modelled debonding between the skin and core. The maximum normal and shear stresses were 2.52 MPa and 1.26 MPa respectively.

The contact was defined between core layers adjacent to the skin-core interface, rather than

between the skin and core. The reason for this approach was to avoid contact problems due to interfaces with two very different material stiffness's contacting each other. It was however, necessary to scale the master and slave stiffness by 100 to avoid penetrations.

Delamination was modelled at all ply-ply interfaces by a similar method to that for debonding, however, damage was modelled using a cohesive zone with a bilinear traction law [13]. Past studies have shown that at least three elements are required in the cohesive zone to accurately capture the crack opening process [13, 14]. In order to know the maximum element size, the length of the cohesive zone, l_{cz} was estimated using the following equation [15]:

$$l_{cz} = E_{33T} \frac{G_{IC}}{(S_{33T})^2} \quad (1)$$

From equation (1) and taking the values from Table 2, the length of the cohesive zone is 1.63 mm. The model had an element length of 0.2 mm in the impact region. Therefore, there were eight elements in the cohesive zone which was considered acceptable.

3.4 Implementation of Pre-load

The model in this study was defined in the undeformed state. The pre-load was introduced as an applied load in an initial analysis step using dynamic relaxation [12, 16]. Dynamic relaxation damps non-rigid-body motions of the structure such that

$$v^{n+1/2} = \eta v^{n-1/2} + a^n \Delta t \quad (2)$$

Where n is the current time step, η is the selected damping factor, a is the nodal acceleration, Δt is the time step size, and v is the nodal velocity.

The computation continued until vibrations had been

damped to an acceptable level, i.e., $\frac{E_{ke}}{E_{ke \max}} < cvtol$,

where E_{ke} and $E_{ke \max}$ are the non-rigid-body kinetic energy and the maximum non-rigid-body kinetic energy respectively, and $cvtol$ is the chosen tolerance.

Pre-tension was applied to only the skins with an appropriate force. Once the loads were initialised, a file was created with the nodal displacement data. A new input file was created with fixed displacements imposed on the edge nodes at their final position. Prior to the impact step of the analysis, the stresses were initialised by applying the nodal displacements from the first step.

4 Results and discussion

The force-time histories for the sandwich laminate with 2 J impact is shown in Fig. 2. The contact duration is inversely proportional to the amount of pre-load. The peak force is proportional to the amount of pre-load as found by previous researchers for laminates [1, 2, 17, 18].

In some cases such as that shown in Fig. 3 for the 2 J case the peak force decreased from 0 to 2500 $\mu\epsilon$ pre-load but then slightly increased for the 5000 $\mu\epsilon$ preload case. This is attributed to an increased amount of damage accumulating from 0 to 2500 $\mu\epsilon$ pre-load, particularly in the grip area as found by Nettles et al. [19]. The damage in the grip area increased again for the 5000 $\mu\epsilon$ pre-load case, but not as much as from 0 to 2500 $\mu\epsilon$ case. This is likely due to the stiffening effects of pre-tension.

No fibre damage was predicted across all models. Damage consisted of delamination and matrix damage in the 90° plies. Delamination was concentrated in the lower plies at 0 preload and in the upper plies when preload was applied.

The top skins behaved as a stand-alone beam rather than the compression surface of a homogenous sandwich beam, thus absorbing most of the impact energy as found by other researchers [13, 20]. Therefore, the bottom skin remained undamaged for the 0 $\mu\epsilon$ case in the impact region (Fig. 4).

Fig. 2. Force-time response of the sandwich coupons for 2 J impact at different pre-load levels

Fig. 3. Force-time response of the sandwich coupons for 2 J impact at for different pre-load levels

Delamination and tensile matrix damage was concentrated in the bottom plies of the top skin for the 0 $\mu\epsilon$ pre-load cases. This is consistent with results from Kim [1]. Damage from these tests on the unloaded laminates was detected throughout the thickness of these specimens, but it tended to accumulate in the bottom plies.

The grip region of the 18 J impact, 0 $\mu\epsilon$ pre-load case sustained additional tensile matrix damage in the upper 90° ply of the bottom skin.

Fig. 5 shows that as pre-load increased, there was less delamination, but more extensive tensile matrix damage in both the top and bottom skins, which was not limited to the tensile side (“Tensile side” refers to the side of the skin that undergoes tension). One may expect that the compressive side will serve to relieve the pre-tension. The likely causes of damage on the compression side at high pre-loads is the shift

of the neutral axis once damage occurred, and the pre-load itself may have caused membrane effects to dominate at smaller deflections.

Fig. 4. Delamination and tensile matrix damage for the 0 $\mu\epsilon$ case and 18 J impact, at the impact region. Red indicates a failed element and black indicates delamination.

Fig. 5. Delamination and tensile matrix plot for the 5000 $\mu\epsilon$ and 18 J impact case at the impact region. Red indicates a failed element and black indicates delamination.

The laminates displayed the same trend of increased damage with increasing pre-load levels with damage not limited to the tensile side. Like the sandwich specimens, there was less delamination and more matrix damage which was not limited to the tensile surface. This change in damage distribution was observed experimentally by Kim [1]. This was not as obvious with the 18 J case where a similar damage distribution between the 0 $\mu\epsilon$ and 5000 $\mu\epsilon$ was introduced. In the 0 $\mu\epsilon$ case, delamination and tensile matrix damage accumulated mostly on the tensile sides as expected, but some tensile matrix damage on the “compressive” side was also present. This damage was present away from the impact region. It is likely that membrane effects were more prevalent than bending due to large deflections.

Compressive matrix damage was also present for the 0 $\mu\epsilon$ case, however, it occurred after the impactor had rebounded from the structure, and thus the skin was bending in the opposite direction.

There was no core debonding for the sandwich laminates except in the 18 J cases shown in Table 3. This can be attributed to the stiffening effects of pre-load [1, 2].

Table 3. Indentation depths and debond lengths for the 18 J case.

	0 $\mu\epsilon$,	2500 $\mu\epsilon$	5000 $\mu\epsilon$
Indentation depth mm	1.90	1.34	0.31
Debond length mm	63.8	57.4	60.8

Debonding initiated earlier for the 0 $\mu\epsilon$ case (at 3.94 ms) than for 2500 $\mu\epsilon$ (6.1 ms). This was possibly due to the higher deflection, where the dynamic unloading of the skins would have acted on the interface for a longer time period with a higher stress concentration factor. In contrast, the pre-load in the 5000 $\mu\epsilon$ case induced a relatively high interface shear stress, thus causing debonding at 5.51 ms and requiring less impact energy to propagate the crack, causing a longer crack length than for the 2500 $\mu\epsilon$ case.

Increasing the amount of pre-load decreased the maximum deflection overall as shown in Table 4. This is attributed to the stiffening effects of pre-load [1, 2]. This study indicates that the effect is greater for the sandwich specimens than for the laminates. This may simply be due to the fact that there was more damage accumulated in the grips for the laminates thus having a softening effect on them.

Table 4. Reduction in max deflection for the top skin at a given velocity for different pre-load levels %. “S” indicates sandwich specimen, “L” indicates laminate.

	Pre-load $\mu\epsilon$			
	0	2500	5000	
E (J)	S2	0.00	42.01	55.29
	S8	0.00	28.79	42.53
	S18	0.00	21.39	33.88
	L2	0.00	36.23	50.61
	L8	0.00	22.80	35.99
	L18	0.00	16.06	27.52

Table 5. Reduction in max deflection for the bottom skin at a given velocity for different pre-load levels %. “S” indicates sandwich specimen.

	Pre-load $\mu\epsilon$			
	0	2500	5000	
E (J)	S2	0	44.51	58.94
	S8	0	31.07	46.53
	S18	0	23.75	38.49

Comparing Table 5 to Table 4 shows that the effect of pre-load was even greater for the bottom skin than it was for the top skin for the sandwich specimens. This may be because the lower indentation in the top skin translates to less core indentation and therefore less densification depths, thus transferring less energy to damage the lower skin.

5 Conclusion

A method has been developed to simulate impact onto a pre-loaded sandwich structure. Reduced integration solids were used for both the skins and the core. A composite damage material modelled the skins, whereas a stress-strain curve was input to model the core behaviour. A convergent solution has been achieved by modelling delamination and debonding by a tied contact algorithm, with the debonding interface being between the core and a thin layer of core solids connected via nodal connectivity to the skin.

An investigation into the effects of pre-load on the impact response of sandwich structures and laminates has been conducted. It was found that more extensive matrix damage was induced in the skin and in both length and through-thickness directions as found by Kim [1]. Delamination appeared to reduce with increasing pre-load which is inconsistent with other research [5]. Future experimental testing will investigate these phenomena.

Compared to a laminate, a sandwich structure has core crushing mechanisms and debonding to include in the analysis. For a given pre-strain, the load is much higher in the skins than the core, thus any change in behaviour from the core per se is negligible. If pre-stress is only applied to the skin the interface between the core and the skin however

can undergo pre-impact shear stresses, thus potentially causing a larger debond region. The stiffening effect of the pre-tension however causes less core indentation thus simultaneously relieving stress on the bond line. Whether more debonding is caused under pre-tension or not will depend on which effect is stronger for the given situation.

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